

On Performance Analysis of Multi-Operator RAN Sharing for Mobile Network Operators

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Abstract: Enhancing the coverage and eliminating the poor performance is key to balance end-user experience and future network investments for mobile network operators (MNOs). Although vast amounts of infrastructure investments are provided by MNOs, there are still coverage and capacity planning problems at remote locations. This is due to fact that in most cases, the population density in those areas are small and return-of-investments are low. In this paper, Radio Access Network (RAN) sharing paradigm is utilized on experimental sites in Turkey to accommodate User Equipment (UEs) of multiple network operators under the same cell sites. We first investigate two different RAN sharing deployment scenarios' characteristics, benefits, and limitations. Then, a city-wide experimental RAN sharing study is conducted on live Long-Term Evolution (LTE) networks between two MNOs, in Turkey. Through experimental tests, we show overall performance gains of enabling RAN sharing feature in terms of observing various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are obtained from shared base stations. Our experimental results demonstrate that both downlink and uplink average user throughput values have increased by 17.8% and 42.85% respectively. After RAN sharing is enabled between MNOs, increase in number of user equipment (UE) due to higher 4G coverage yielded higher number of inter-Radio Access Technology (RAT) handover attempts. This resulted inter-RAT handover out success rate to decrease by 70.66%. Intra-frequency handover out success rate, which indicates if the subscriber is using the same RAT type, has increased by 358.33% and service drop rates have dropped 86.1% respectively, after RAN sharing is enabled. Finally, we discuss and summarize the main takeaways of the outcome of the considered large-scale RAN sharing experiments.

Key words: mobile-operator, radio access network, transport, network sharing, real-world testbed

1. Introduction

5G has just begun to be installed in some countries and it is anticipated that installation will accelerate in the future. However, considering the investments in 5G devices in terms of operators, the costs of 5G infrastructure will be thought-provoking. One of the negative thoughts about 5G investments may seem to be that operators are still not making enough profits with their Long Term Evolution (LTE) investments (including newer devices, infrastructure and operational costs)¹. In addition to those mentioned among the costs to be paid for 5G, there are also costs for the spectrum, which can have a significant financial impact on operators. In this case, network sharing applications based on common usage of equipment can be a suitable solution. Among these, Radio

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¹GSM.A. 5G-era Mobile Network Cost Evolution. <https://www.gsm.a.com/futurenetworks/wiki/5g-era-mobile-network-cost-evolution/>, 2019.

Figure 1: Multi operator core network based RAN sharing scenario.

1 Access Network (RAN) sharing appears to be a solution that can provide reduced infrastructure and device
 2 costs for operators due to high utilization of different and advanced techniques in radio access ².

3 The term of RAN sharing was first introduced in The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)
 4 Release-5 and at that time it was designed for 3G as Multi-Operator Core Network (MOCN). RAN sharing is
 5 specified in 3GPP Technical Study (TS) [1] as multiple operators are operating their own Core Network (CN)
 6 and share a common RAN infrastructure. Until the introduction of the Release-14 by 3GPP, MOCN was realised
 7 by RAN connectivity to multiple CNs with a System Information Block (SIB) structure indicating a single cell
 8 Identifier (ID) and Tracking Area Code (TAC) associated with a list of Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN)
 9 IDs as detailed in TS of 3GPP [2]. A RAN node's identifier namely the eNB-ID contains the ID of the cells that
 10 are serving. Multiple CNs are connected to a single RAN operator with an associated Cell-ID/TAC numbering
 11 space dedicated to them as shown in Fig. 1. For LTE as described in Rel-14 of 3GPP, a new SIB structure was
 12 introduced that allows RAN separation by broadcasting multiple Cell-IDs. Thus, each Cell-ID/TAC association
 13 is allowed to be dedicated to one Mobile Network Operator (MNO) only. This enhancement in the SIB aims
 14 to support RAN-only service provider deployment use cases, where logical separation of RANs is needed. For
 15 5G cases, MOCN with multiple Cell-ID broadcast was specified from the beginning the Release-15 of 3GPP.
 16 Each Cell-ID corresponds to a RAN node's identifier and multiple Cell-IDs correspond to multiple logical RAN
 17 nodes as shown in Fig. 2. In cases where gNBs are disaggregated into gNB-Distributed Units (DUs) and gNB-
 18 Central Units (CUs), multiple Cell-ID allows logically separated F1 interface instances where each instance is
 19 established and maintained individually. For example, three 5G operators can use two broadcast Cell-IDs, so
 20 that two operators can share the same Cell-ID/TAC space which is different than the LTE based deployment.

21 1.1. Related Work

22 In real-world network deployments, RAN sharing is utilized by most of the major MNOs in the world. For
 23 example, Vodafone shares RAN in multiple regions of Spain and this collaboration covers a mixture of 2G, 3G
 24 and LTE technologies. The other operator that is sharing RAN with Vodafone in Spain is Orange ³. Another
 25 example of network sharing agreement is between Vodafone and O2 that covers the 5G deployment in Britain
 26 ⁴. One of the important factors that affect the efficiency and economic gains of RAN sharing is providing a
 27 fairness between different MNOs [4], [5]. If the fairness is provided, the shared equipment can cover all types of

²GSMA. Infrastructure Sharing: An Overview. <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/wiki/infrastructure-sharing-an-overview/>, 2019.

³Orange Press Release, <https://www.orange.com/en/Press-Room/press-releases/press-releases-2019/Orange-and-Vodafone-strengthen-their-mobile-and-fixed-network-sharing-agreements-in-Spain>, 2019.

⁴O2 Press Release, <https://news.o2.co.uk/press-release/o2-and-vodafone-finalise-5g-network-agreement-in-the-uk/>, 2019.

Figure 2: An Illustration of RAN sharing for 5G use cases.

1 devices in the network such as femtocells, smallcells and macrocells [6].

2 In the centralized or cloud RAN (C-RAN in short) based scenarios which include the CU and DU
 3 split, RAN sharing deployment includes the sharing of the centralized resource computing elements [7]. The
 4 authors in [8–10] have benefited from Software-Defined Networking (SDN)-based C-RAN architecture to enable
 5 sharing of network resources among multiple MNO. Efficient resource scheduling in multi-tenant environments
 6 is very important and scheduling functions need to be investigated [11], [12] when user behaviours such as
 7 mobility change in different parts of the mobile networks. In multi-tenant environments, a robust procedure
 8 of leasing resources from infrastructure providers dynamically via signaling is needed [13]. Since cloud RAN is
 9 not standardized under 3GPP, 3GPP defined sharing scenarios need to be studied for mapping these scenarios
 10 into the cloud RAN perspective. The article in [14] studied this mapping and evaluated the results obtained in
 11 simulation environment. Another article in [15] extended the study in [14] and investigates the all aspects of
 12 the cloud based 5G networks.

13 The Base Station (BS) that is used for the sharing purposes among different MNOs, the Quality-of-Service
 14 (QoS) requests coming from the user equipments (UEs) belonging to different MNOs are realized by that BS
 15 via keeping separate lists [16]. For the CN side, to ease the load of the BS that is serving to different CNs can
 16 be solved by using CN multiplexing [17]. Since each MNO has a separate PLMN identifier, the handling of
 17 broadcasting different PLMNs is critical [18]. In [25], simulation results show that information-centric wireless
 18 network virtualization architecture outperforms the other existing schemes including RAN sharing. The network
 19 slicing can be thought as a different version of network sharing and this concept brings an end-to-end logical
 20 network that runs on a shared infrastructure. In the network slicing concept RAN, transport and CN resources
 21 for the network provider are abstracted and these abstracted resources can then be assigned to different MNOs
 22 in dynamic or dedicated manner [19], [26]. Evaluation of sharing in software-defined radio based deployment is
 23 discussed in [20] but can be evaluated as a difficult use case when considering the current hardware capabilities
 24 of telecommunication vendors.

25 The study in [21] investigates a novel effective scheduler and admission control mechanisms for shared
 26 RAN with system level simulations. The authors in [27] build an emulation setup to connect a BS to multiple
 27 CNs via a RAN Proxy (RANP) box to achieve RAN sharing. Fairness issues in RAN sharing between multiple
 28 MNOs are investigated in [4, 28] and RAN sharing for public safety and railway networks is analyzed in [29]
 29 via simulations. The authors in [30] study handover parameter optimization to overcome the network coverage
 30 problem of MOCN scenario in RAN sharing. The paper in [31] analyzes the benefits of RAN and spectrum

1 sharing paradigms using a modified version of SimuLTE model to create a simulation environment. Nevertheless,
 2 these studies do not present a complete view on large-scale real network deployment use cases.

3 **1.2. Main Contributions**

4 To best of authors' knowledge, few works have considered the experimental evaluations of RAN sharing and
 5 their corresponding Key Parameter Indicator (KPI) results in a city-wide deployment scenario. Moreover, none
 6 of the works above have evaluated different deployment options or scenarios of RAN sharing flavors and studied
 7 their characteristics, limitations and advantages. Our main contributions in this paper can be summarized as
 8 follows: (a) investigate different configuration options and deployment scenarios for RAN sharing and study their
 9 characteristics, benefits, and limitations. (b) investigate the challenges of deploying RAN sharing scenarios in
 10 both transport network and RAN domains. (c) analyze the experimental KPI outcomes of one of the considered
 11 RAN sharing network scenario (called as *MOCN as Multi-Operator Radio Access Network (MORAN)*) for two
 12 MNOs in one of the pilot city in Turkey in a realistic environment. Our experimental results demonstrate that
 13 both Download (DL) and Upload (UL) average user throughput values have increased by 17.8% and 42.85%
 14 respectively, inter-RAT Handover (HO) out success rate and service drop rates have decreased by 70.66% and
 15 86.1% respectively whereas intra-frequency HO out success rate has increased by 358.33% after RAN sharing
 16 is enabled in the network.

17 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 is presenting the different architectures and
 18 deployment options for enabling RAN sharing among multiple MNOs. Section 3 provides the RAN and transport
 19 network related important parameters that need to be managed and corresponding challenges that can be
 20 encountered during enabling RAN sharing among multiple MNOs. Section 4 provides the experimental results
 21 and discusses about outcomes of the shared RAN system based on the obtained results. Finally, Section 5 gives
 22 the conclusions and the future work.

23 **2. System Architecture for Deployment Options**

24 In this section, we introduce different and possible deployment options that are supported by the mobile network
 25 nodes. RAN sharing allows resource sharing between MNOs. Additionally, RAN feature enables each MNOs to
 26 use their own PLMN over the same RAN. Without RAN sharing, a PLMN consists of a RAN and a CN, through
 27 which each MNO provides services to their subscribers, while subscribers of other MNOs can only receive services
 28 as national or international roamers. These configurations are standardized scenarios for network sharing as in
 29 3GPP TS [1]. There are various types of deployment configurations for RAN sharing as shown in Figure 3 which
 30 provides both 3GPP compliant and non-3GPP configuration options. In all RAN sharing options, some parts of
 31 the network equipment are shared between MNOs (which are marked with red color in Figure 3). For example
 32 in scenario #2, Base Band Unit (BBU) is shared whereas in scenario #3, BBU, Radio Remote Unit (RRU) and
 33 Mobility Management Entity (MME) are shared among MNOs. Note that maximum amount of sharing units
 34 (therefore maximum benefit in terms of cost) can be accomplished in scenario #6 where network equipment of
 35 Serving Gateway (S-GW), MME and BS (RRU and BBU) units are shared between MNOs. Shared spectrum
 36 can be achieved with scenarios #2, #3 and #4, separate spectrum is achieved with scenarios #6 and #7
 37 and both spectrum sharing and separate spectrum options are available in scenario #5. 3GPP compliance and
 38 specifications are accomplished with five of the scenarios #2, #3, #5, #6 and #7 whereas scenario #1 and
 39 #4 are not 3GPP compliant. Therefore, we can conclude that there are different consequences of deploying
 40 each of these scenarios for RAN sharing. The details of each deployment scenarios and options including their

Figure 3: Different configuration options for RAN Sharing.

1 characteristics, advantages and corresponding challenges for MNOs are described in Table 1.

2 3. Challenges of RAN Sharing

3 There are multiple challenges of establishing RAN sharing between multiple MNO over multiple network
 4 domains. In this section, we will detail some of the related constraints in both RAN and transport network.

5 3.1. RAN Related Constraints

6 There are some important features and their corresponding challenges that need to be re-considered during
 7 RAN sharing deployments. These are described as follows:

8 **PLMN handling:** Many MNOs can share a single LTE RAN, thus PLMN handling is important to provide
 9 correct PLMN information. Mobility candidate selection determines a set of frequencies in LTE or other Radio
 10 Access Technologys (RATs), to which the connected UE can be transferred when it encounters poor coverage
 11 in the current cell. In the shared RAN scenario, different UE are connected to networks belonging to different
 12 MNOs. To avoid UE belonging to one operator being redirected or handed over to another operator network, an
 13 allowed PLMN list is added to each frequency relation of MNO for all RATs. If the list is empty, the frequency
 14 relation is allowed for UE belonging to any PLMN. If the list contains at least one PLMN, the frequency
 15 relation is only allowed for UEs that have at least one of the listed PLMN as serving PLMN or equivalent PLMN. In
 16 this way, PLMN interconnection problem can be solved easily [22].

17 **SIB information:** It contains relevant information when evaluating whether a UE is allowed to access a cell
 18 and also defines the scheduling of other system information. For each cell, the SIB can include more than one
 19 PLMN and it must include all active PLMNs. The primary PLMN must always be broadcast in the SIB. This
 20 is due to fact that it is used to construct the Cell Global Identity (CGI) and used by the UE to identify the

TABLE 1
COMPARISONS OF THE DIFFERENT SCENARIOS FOR RAN SHARING DEPLOYMENT.

Scenario	Characteristics	Challenges	Advantages
1. Site Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Both MNOs position their eNodeBs at same location. — All the CN equipment are separate — All the cells and frequencies belongs to the MNOs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — OPeX saving is questionable — Two set of operations under the same physical space. — Agreement is needed among MNOs for suitable site selection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Share the energy resources and site leasing costs. — No software configurations are needed for BBUs. — The least complex sharing scenario in terms of network configuration.
2. MOCN as MORAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Separate carriers can be used at the RAN side. — Cells are connected to the operator owned carriers and one shared BBU is used for transport traffic aggregation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — A highly capable BBU needed to operate with the different carriers. — Complexity in management of BBU — Ownership of BBU is questionable — Needs agreements on QoS policies due to single BBU. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Fully compliant with regulation authority rules. — Each MNO aggregate mobile traffic in their owned carrier frequencies. — No additional BBU investment. — QoS configuration is relatively less complex when compared with other MORAN scenarios.
3. GWCN as MORAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Both eNodeB and MME are shared by two or more MNOs. — By network configuration non-shared cells can be enabled (dedicated frequency for each operator.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Authentication of BS is done at shared MME (can bring security issues). — Agreement issues on parameter adjustments of CP signalling among MNOs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Reduces the number of CP signalling. — No additional MME & BBU investment
4. MORAN with 2BBUs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Two DUs or BBU units that belong to different MNOs can share radio units and the support system. — Operators have their own carriers and individual configuration of all parameters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Not compliant with 3GPP standards. — Spectrum configuration is hard due to shared RRUs. — Interconnection between BBUs brings operational complexity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No additional RRU investments. — Agreements on QoS configuration is possible due to separate BBUs.
5. Geographical split	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Two or more MNOs are serving to the different geographical locations across the country. — Collaborative large scale network deployment among MNOs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — MNOs need to obey each other site selection and deployment policies. — Providing QoS and cost saving is questionable due to different MNO subscriber distributions in different regions across the country. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Spectrum sharing can be selected or not based on the implementation and regulative constraints.
6. GWCN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — The eNodeB and the MME are shared by two or more MNOs. — SGW can also be shared based on deployment. — All the cells and frequencies are shared. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — More suitable to MVNOs not for MNOs (due to high number of virtualized nodes). — Regulation licence of MVNOs may be required for MNOs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Best scenario for OPEX and CAPEX saving. (due to shared MME, SGW and BBU) — No additional interconnection needed between MNOs
7. MOCN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Two or more MNOs share one eNodeB while the core network is dedicated for each operator. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Operation is difficult since ownership of BS is questionable. — Regulation difficulties due to traffic aggregation at same nodes (both in BBU and carrier). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No additional carries and BBU investments. — Relatively easy configuration when compared to MORAN (scenario 2 and 4).

cell. If the Primary PLMN is excluded as the active PLMN, the primary PLMN is marked as reserved for MNO usage in the SIB.

Mobility & Handover cases: When UE reports that it has found a set of suitable cells based on its LTE measurements, a handover evaluation process is executed. Handover evaluation decides whether a reported cell is suitable for that UE. The Tracking Area Identifier (TAI) of the target cell is compared with the forbidden TAIs. If all the reported cells are forbidden for the UE, the report is discarded. If it is still valid, then the target cell PLMN or PLMN list is compared with the UE serving PLMN and equivalent PLMNs. If there is a match between them, the best cell is selected as target cell. In RAN sharing, since X2 handover signaling is only allowed if the eNodeBs are connected to the same MME pool, the target eNodeB MME pools must be compared with the UE serving MME before X2 handover is selected instead of S1 handover. If the target eNodeB is not connected to the MME pool to which the UE serving MME belongs, X2 handover is not allowed. In case of Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN), the maximum number of frequencies depend on the compliance of the UE with 3GPP Release-12 below or higher. All PLMNs have a common configuration for S1-U and S1-MME. However, if multiple Internet Protocol (IP) addresses are needed, then it is possible to use different configurations for each PLMN independently.

3.2. Transport Network Related Constraints

Along with the target transmission network architecture, RAN sharing is also aimed to create a shared transmission network, provide error isolation, load sharing and create an architecture ready for convergence of the shared network. The transport network for the shared RAN can also utilize network automation techniques as described in [23], [24]. The transport network topology in RAN sharing is different than traditional transport network topology. Fig. 4 shows the topology concentrated on the transport side. The overall traffic from/to the shared BS will reach to the Mobile Backhaul Aggregation Router (MBAR) of the first MNO (which is MNO-1 in Fig. 4). Then, there are separate peering routers that are positioned between MNOs (i.e. between MNO-1 & MNO-2 and MNO-1 & MNO-3). Corresponding peering routers are in communication with the Circuit Switched (CS)-Packet-Switched (PS) CN of each MNOs. Multi-Protocol (MP)-Border Gateway Protocol (BGP) model is recommended for traffic transmission between two MNOs. BGP connection will be provided over local Autonomous System (AS) numbers. In this case, each service will be carried through a separate Virtual Private Network (VPN). To prevent problems in case of ever increasing interconnections between regions in future, a separate prefix list should be created for each service. Note that, each user traffic belonging to different MNOs are separated by Virtual LANs (VLANs) between the MBAR and the shared BSs. Thus, one leased line can be configured with three VLANs.

On the RAN side, the same scheduling rate should be set for QoS Class Identifier (QCI)-8 and QCI-9. On the transport side, the queue from QCI-8 and 9 must be carried within best effort priority. According to the traffic value from the opposite MNO, marking will be done in the peering router in the direction of ingress. Note that all of the MNOs will not have premium users in the sharing area. Secure tunnels are opened towards Security Gateway (SecGW) of the guest MNO with the certificate information received by the Certification Authority (CA) server. Certificate update should also be done automatically and certificate traffic must be carried over a separate VPN. After certification process is accomplished successfully, there will be separate IP Security (IPSec) tunnels that will be established to the SecGWs of the different MNOs.

Another situation to be noted here is related to the number of interconnections. As an example, let's assume that there is one interconnection point for the whole country and this is in the center of the country.

Figure 4: Topology of the target transport network.

1 In this case, the traffic of the BSs in the cities that are located at the edge of the country comes to the
 2 center location and goes from there to the CN of the other operator. Hence, the transport network creates
 3 network-induced delays. Interconnection can be made in more than one place in the country, but it will cause
 4 interconnection investments such as peering routers and leased lines.

5 4. Experimental Results

6 During our experimental trials, RAN sharing is enabled between 29 October 2018 to 04 November 2018 (7
 7 days) and comparisons are made when no RAN sharing is enabled on dates between 02 January 2018 to 15
 8 January 2018 (14 days) for LTE systems. Our experimentally tested RAN sharing network scenario is *MOCN*
 9 *as MORAN* for two MNOs as illustrated in Fig. 3. Before RAN sharing was enabled, each MNO had 50 sites
 10 scattered around the city and the measurement campaign is done for MNO-1. For RAN sharing, 70 newly
 11 added sites are selected for experimenting *MOCN as MORAN* scenario among two MNOs in Turkey. Those
 12 sites are selected jointly by two MNOs that are involved in active RAN sharing trial. Investigated KPI values
 13 during our experimental trial are Radio Resource Control (RRC) setup success rate, E-UTRAN Radio Access
 14 Bearer (E-RAB) setup success rate, service drop rate, intra-frequency HO out success rate, inter-RAT HO out
 15 success rate, Circuit Switched FallBack (CSFB) success rate, user DL and UL average throughput. All related
 16 KPIs are calculated by averaging the hourly values of the considered sites.

17 RRC setup success rate KPI simply measures successful attachment counts of UEs into the network
 18 during RRC connection request of UEs which can be formulated as

$$RRCSetup_{SR} = \frac{\# \text{ of } RRCSetupSuccess}{\# \text{ of } RRCSetupAttempt} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

19 where *RRCSetupSuccess* is RRC connection establishment's success count and *RRCSetupAttempt* is RRC
 20 connection establishments attempt count. After successful RRC connection, the network goes from *RRC_idle*
 21 mode to *RRC_connected* mode. Some possible practical reasons for observing low RRC setup success rates in
 22 a call are related to resource allocation failure (due to UE admission failures) or no response from UE (due to

Figure 5: 4G average throughput KPIs (a) User DL average throughput. (b) User UL average throughput.

1 poor coverage or terminal problem).

2 An E-RAB carries the service data of UEs as an access layer bearer. E-RAB setup success rate is related
 3 to accessibility and E-RAB counter KPI is utilized after successful RRC connection. The E-RAB success rate
 4 depends on successful connections to CN which can be formulated as

$$ERABSetUp_{SR} = \frac{\# \text{ of } ERABSetUpSuccess}{\# \text{ of } ERABSetUpAttempt} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

5 where $ERABSetUpSuccess$ is successful E-RAB establishments and $ERABSetUpAttempt$ is received E-RAB
 6 establishment attempts.

7 A CS capable device that is registered to LTE needs to fall back to 3G (or even 2G) before a call is
 8 terminated is originated. For this reason, many MNOs have integrate CSFB feature so that voice services
 9 can be offered to LTE UE without the support of additional investments (e.g Voice over LTE (VoLTE)). The
 10 following formula is used to calculate CSFB Success Ratio

$$CSFB_{SR} = \frac{\# \text{ of } CSFBSuccess}{\# \text{ of } CSFBAttempt} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

11 where $CSFBSuccess$ is successful CSFB attempts and $CSFBAttempt$ is all CSFB attempt.

12 Intra-frequency HO out success rate ($IntraFreqHOOut_{SR}$ in short) is defined as the success rate of
 13 intra-frequency HOs from local cell to neighbouring cells and is calculated as

$$IntraFreqHOOut_{SR} = \frac{\# \text{ of } IntraFreqHOOutSuccess}{\# \text{ of } IntraFreqHOOutAttempt} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

14 Similarly, inter-RAT HO outgoing success rate ($InterRATHOOut_{SR}$ in short) is defined as the success
 15 rate of outgoing handovers from 4G cell to other different 3GPP and non-3GPP type cells (e.g. 2G, 3G cells,
 16 etc) and is calculated as

$$InterRATHOOut_{SR} = \frac{\# \text{ of } InterRATHOOutSuccess}{\# \text{ of } InterRATHOOutAttempt} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

17 Fig. 5 shows the changes in 4G average UL and DL throughput, before and after RAN sharing is enabled
 18 in the considered sites. We can observe that both DL and UL average user throughput values have increased
 19 by 17.8% and 42.85% respectively after RAN sharing is enabled in the network. This signifies that the load on

1 the considered MNO has increased after the addition of more UEs of another MNOs in the experimental region.
 2 This indicates that 4G network coverage after enabling RAN sharing has increased significantly. Fig. 6 shows
 3 the change in HO related KPIs after enabling RAN sharing. This figure shows that inter-RAT HO out success
 4 rate and service drop rates have decreased by 70.66% and 86.1% respectively whereas intra-frequency HO out
 5 success rate has increased by 358.33% after RAN sharing is enabled in the network. Note that interference
 6 levels can have huge impact on the HO success rate values. A huge increase in intra-frequency HO success rate
 7 indicates that the interference level in BSs has diminished significantly and UEs with different ranges of speed
 8 can successfully perform HOs between cells with much higher success rates. As a matter of fact, observing
 9 low values in inter-RAT handovers outgoing success rate in Fig. 6(a) is not a desirable outcome when network
 10 optimization and capacity planning are planned by MNOs. One of the major reason is that the handover
 11 between technologies (e.g. from 4G to 3G) is undesired by MNOs as it can cause unpredictable consequences on
 12 user's Quality-of-Experience (QoE). Hence, homogeneous 4G coverage distribution in large geographical regions
 13 is preferred. On the other hand in our shared RAN implementation, one can easily observe that the usage of
 14 4G technology has increased due to increased usage of UEs with 4G capability after RAN sharing. However, 3G
 15 technology coverage has remained constant as no major upgrades are done in terms of 3G coverage expansion
 16 during the experimental trial duration. For this reason after RAN sharing is enabled between MNOs, increase
 17 in number of UEs due to higher 4G coverage has yielded higher number of inter-RAT handover attempts. As a
 18 consequence of this, inter-RAT handover out success rate has decreased.

19 Fig. 7 shows the changes in connection related KPIs after enabling RAN sharing. From Fig. 7, the RRC
 20 setup success rate, E-RAB setup success rate and CSFB success rate have increased very slightly by 0.01%,
 21 0.04% and 0.7% respectively after RAN sharing is enabled. Therefore, we can say RRC and E-RAB setup
 22 success rates that have been relatively stable. CSFB success rate values have also observed to be higher after

Figure 6: 4G handover KPIs (a) Inter-RAT handover outgoing success rate. (b) Intra-frequency handover outgoing success rate. (c) Service drop rate.

1 enabling RAN sharing feature. This is in fact related to 4G coverage expansion outcome of the RAN sharing.
 2 On the other hand, we can also observe that CSFB success values have also not increased substantially. This can
 3 be related to low percentage of UEs utilizing VoLTE services in comparisons with the total increasing number
 4 of UE utilizing LTE network.

5 E-RAB setup request and response are established between eNodeB and core network of MNOs. E-RAB
 6 success rate is related to availability of radio resources and RRC connected number of users. No significant
 7 changes in E-RAB success rate in Fig. 7 indicate that before and after active RAN sharing trial, the UEs
 8 were able to reach CN successfully. Hence no major failures have induced in both radio and core network
 9 during E-RAB setup before and after RAN sharing. After RAN sharing is enabled, the number of 4G UEs has
 10 increased due to LTE coverage extension. However, RRC setup and E-RAN success rates are kept relatively
 11 constant with no major changes after enabling RAN sharing. In E-RAB connection, the locations of core
 12 networks for both MNOs were unchanged after RAN sharing feature is enabled. Hence, while RAN sharing
 13 feature is activated during experiments, the core network locations are kept separate for both MNOs in same
 14 city. However these locations were in a different city from the location where RAN sharing is performed.
 15 Therefore, transport network were also shared between MNOs. Each UE traffic belonging to different MNOs
 16 are separated by VLANs between the MBAR and the shared BSs. Thus, one leased line is configured with three
 17 VLANs. The purpose of transport network sharing was to focus on Operational expenditure (OPEX)/Capital
 18 Expenditure (CAPEX) savings. In fact, the transport path to the core network did not become shorter in terms
 19 of distance after RAN sharing is enabled. For this reason, the E-RAB success rate has remained the same
 20 due to no major differences on the length and performance of the transport network path. These results again
 21 validates the increase in UE throughput values is due to improvements done in RAN domain due to active RAN
 22 sharing feature. The outcome of the experiments have also demonstrated that the scheduler of eNodeBs has
 23 been successful in scheduling new arriving UEs appropriately since no significant changes have occurred during
 24 RRC setup. This signifies that the buffer size were not full and there were enough resources to assign to newly
 25 arriving UE RRC connection request during experiments.

26 Note that among the discussed RAN sharing mechanisms explained in Section 2, we have demonstrated
 27 scenario #2: *MOCN as MORAN* in our experiments instead of scenario #7: *MOCN*. It is known that simple
 28 *MOCN* scheme improves the interference levels in network but suffers from network coverage issues [30]. The
 29 main difference compared to *MOCN* is that high capacity and costly BBU needed to be utilized in *MOCN as*
 30 *MORAN* scenario since the carriers are separated for each MNO. Since the processing and computing power
 31 of this BBU was higher, this has also improved the QoS provided to UEs. Another major advantage of using
 32 *MOCN as MORAN* was the ability of each MNO to utilize their own carriers or frequencies. This has given
 33 much flexibility and higher total bandwidth to MNOs compared to shared carrier frequency case of *MOCN*
 34 scenario.

35 During activation of RAN sharing feature, new and optimized BS locations are selected by two MNOs
 36 jointly. This has also improved the utilization of cell towers and hence the coverage significantly, as can be
 37 observed from the improvements in both UL and DL user average throughput values in Fig. 5. Moreover,
 38 careful selection of a joint QoS policy by two MNOs has also resulted in higher improvements in throughput
 39 values due to lower interference values in coverage areas even though relatively stable values in both RRC and
 40 E-RAB setup success rates are observed. On the other hand, RAN sharing activation has also made a major
 41 impact on the utilization of services provided by MNO during live trial period. UL traffic values have increased
 42 more than DL traffic values as given in Fig. 5. This signifies that UEs have started to utilize UL services (e.g.
 43 multimedia sharing, image and video uploads, etc.) after RAN sharing is enabled in the network. This is also

Figure 7: 4G KPIs (a) RRC setup success rate. (b) E-RAB setup success rate. (c) CSFB success rate.

1 a consequence of lower service drop rates that are observed in Figure 6(c) after RAN sharing is enabled.

2 5. Conclusions and Future Work

3 In this paper, we have investigated RAN sharing solution and their possible deployment scenarios together with
 4 their characteristics, advantages and limitations. In addition to that, city-wide experimental studies of one of
 5 the considered *MOCN as MORAN* scenario in RAN sharing are performed on operational LTE networks in
 6 Turkey. Through experimental tests, we showed the overall performance gains of enabling RAN sharing feature
 7 in terms of observing different KPIs that are obtained from shared BSs. In particular, both DL and UL average
 8 user throughput values have increased by 17.8% and 42.85% respectively, inter-RAT HO out success rate and
 9 service drop rates have decreased by 70.66% and 86.1% respectively whereas intra-frequency HO out success
 10 rate has increased by 358.33% after RAN sharing is enabled in the network.

11 One of the relevant topics that can be studied as a future study is to investigate whether RAN sharing
 12 paradigm can also be applied during network slicing environment. Although this issue has been solved partly for
 13 the shared slicing structure, investigation of the RAN sharing application for the cases where dedicated slicing
 14 is used can be considered as one of the topics for future work. Another important topic of interest is that in
 15 cases where there is a cloud RAN structure, details of how to handle RAN sharing can be investigated as well.

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References

- 1 [1] 3rd Generation Partnership Project. Network Sharing; Architecture and functional description (Release 15). 3GPP
2 TS 23.251 V15.1.0, 2018.
- 3 [2] 3rd Generation Partnership Project. Intra-domain connection of Radio Access Network (RAN) nodes to multiple
4 Core Network (CN) nodes (Release 15). 3GPP TS 23.236 V15.0.0, 2018.
- 5 [3] Chien H., Lin Y., Chang H. and Lai C. Multi-Operator Fairness in Transparent RAN Sharing by Soft-Partition
6 With Blocking and Dropping Mechanism. IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology 2018; 67(12):11597-11605.
7 doi: 10.1109/TVT.2018.2872042.
- 8 [4] Hsu-Tung C. et al. Multi-Operator Fairness in Transparent RAN Sharing by Soft-Partition With Block-
9 ing and Dropping Mechanism. IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology 2018; 67(12):11597-11605. doi:
10 10.1109/TVT.2018.2872042
- 11 [5] Lin Y., Chien H. , Chang H. and Lai C. Multi-operator Fairness in Transparent RAN Sharing. In: Proceedings
12 of IEEE International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC); Maui, HI; 2018. pp.
13 259-263.
- 14 [6] Lin Y., Chien H., Chang H., Lai C. and Lin K. Transparent RAN Sharing of 5G Small Cells and Macrocells. IEEE
15 Wireless Communications 2017; 24(6):104-111. doi: 10.1109/MWC.2017.1600372
- 16 [7] Tran T. X. and Pompili D. Dynamic Radio Cooperation for User-Centric Cloud-RAN With Computing Resource
17 Sharing. IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications 2017; 16(4):2379-2393,. doi: 10.1109/TWC.2017.2664823
- 18 [8] Narmanlioglu O.and Zeydan E. New era in shared C-RAN and core network: A case study for efficient RRH usage.
19 In: Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC); Paris, France; 2017, pp. 1-7
- 20 [9] Narmanlioglu O.and Zeydan E. New Era in shared cellular networks: Moving into open and virtualized platform.
21 International Journal of Network Management 2017; 27.6: 1-19. doi: 10.1002/nem.1986
- 22 [10] Narmanlioglu O., Zeydan E., and Arslan S. S. Service-aware multi-resource allocation in software-defined next
23 generation cellular networks. IEEE Access 2018; 6: 20348-20363. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2818751
- 24 [11] Khan S. N., Goratti L., Riggio R. and Hasan S. On active, fine-grained RAN and spectrum sharing in multi-tenant
25 5G networks. In: Proceedings of IEEE 28th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile
26 Radio Communications (PIMRC); Montreal, QC; 2017. pp. 1-5.
- 27 [12] Park S., Simeone O. and Shamai S. Multi-Tenant C-RAN With Spectrum Pooling: Downlink Optimiza-
28 tion Under Privacy Constraints. IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology 2018; 67(11):10492-10503,. doi:
29 10.1109/TVT.2018.2865599
- 30 [13] Samdanis K., Costa-Perez X. and Sciancalepore V. From network sharing to multi-tenancy: The 5G network slice
31 broker. IEEE Communications Magazine 2016; 54(7):32-39. doi: 10.1109/MCOM.2016.7514161
- 32 [14] M. A. Marotta et al. Resource sharing in heterogeneous cloud radio access networks. IEEE Wireless Communications
33 2015; 22(3):74-82. doi: 10.1109/MWC.2015.7143329
- 34 [15] Yu R., Ding J., Huang X., Zhou M., Gjessing S. and Zhang Y. Optimal Resource Sharing in 5G-Enabled Vehicular
35 Networks: A Matrix Game Approach. IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology 2016; 65(10):7844-7856. doi:
36 10.1109/TVT.2016.2536441
- 37 [16] Timus B., Kallin H. and Mildh G. Full and partial resource access in RAN sharing. US Patent: US9596698B2
- 38 [17] Morper H. and Markwart C. Multiplexing core networks in RAN sharing. US Patent: US9615318B2
- 39 [18] Byun D. and Xu J. Method and device for base station supporting RAN sharing. US Patent: US20180288815A1
- 40 [19] Ksentini A. and Nikaiein N. Toward Enforcing Network Slicing on RAN: Flexibility and Resources Abstraction.
41 IEEE Communications Magazine 2017; 55(6):102-108. doi: 10.1109/MCOM.2017.1601119
- 42

- 1 [20] Foukas X., Nikaen N., Kassem M. M., Marina M. K., and Kontovasilis K. FlexRAN: A Flexible and Programmable
2 Platform for Software-Defined Radio Access Networks. In: Proceedings of the 12th International on Conference on
3 emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies (CoNEXT '16). Association for Computing Machinery, New
4 York, NY; 2016, USA, 427–441.
- 5 [21] Guo T. and Arnott R. Active LTE RAN Sharing with Partial Resource Reservation. In: Proceedings of IEEE 78th
6 Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC Fall); Vegas, NV; 2013, pp. 1-5.
- 7 [22] 3GPP TS 29.573 V16.1.0.5G System; Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) Interconnection, Stage 3 (Release 16),
8 2019.
- 9 [23] Turk Y., Zeydan E., Mercimek I. F. and Danisman E. HUBBLE: An Optical Link Management System for Dense
10 Wavelength Division Multiplexing Networks. Turkish Journal Elect. Eng. & Comp. Sciences, 2019; doi: 10.3906/elk-
11 1904-207
- 12 [24] Turk Y., Zeydan E., Mercimek I. F. and Danisman E. Unified and Automated Fault Management Platform for
13 Optical Networks. In: Proceedings of the Network Traffic Measurement and Analysis Conference (TMA), Paris,
14 France; 2019, 2019, 197-198.
- 15 [25] Liang C., Yu F. R. and Zhang, X. Toward Information-centric network function virtualization over 5g mobile wireless
16 networks. IEEE Network, 2015; 29(3):68-74-108. doi: 10.1109/MNET.2015.7113228
- 17 [26] Afolabi I., Taleb T., Samdanis K., Ksentini A. and Flinc H. Toward Network Slicing and Softwarization: A Survey
18 on Principles, Enabling Technologies, and Solutions. IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials 2018; 20(3):2429-
19 2453. doi: 10.1109/COMST.2018.2815638
- 20 [27] Ying-Dar L. et al. Transparent RAN sharing of 5G small cells and macrocells. IEEE Wireless Communications
21 2017; 24(6):104-11. doi: 10.1109/MWC.2017.1600372
- 22 [28] Ying-Dar L. et al. Multi-operator Fairness in Transparent RAN Sharing. In: Proceedings of the International
23 Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC); Maui HI, USA; 2018, pp. 1-5
- 24 [29] Ahmad I., Wan C. and Chang K. LTE-railway user priority-based cooperative resource allocation schemes for
25 coexisting public safety and railway networks. IEEE Access 2017; 5: 7985-8000. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2698098
- 26 [30] Hyunwoo K. et al. Network coverage expansion in radio access network sharing. In: Proceedings of Sixth Interna-
27 tional Conference on Future Generation Communication Technologies (FGCT); Dublin, Ireland; 2017, 1-5.
- 28 [31] Shah Nawaz K. et al. On active, fine-grained RAN and spectrum sharing in multi-tenant 5G networks. In: Proceed-
29 ings of the IEEE 28th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Communications
30 (PIMRC); Montreal, QC, Canada; 2017, 1-5.